

**Discussion Paper on China,
the South China Sea, and the
Options of a Small State like
The Philippines**

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Understanding China

China's development into a modern state did not follow the same view and logic as most countries in the West. Its history and experiences, from the Qing dynasty up until the Communist regime, informs the plans and actions of its leadership.

The Middle Kingdom¹

From its unification in 221 B.C. under the Qin dynasty until the early 20th century under the Qing dynasty, its elites and its people consider China as the central and civilized part of the world or "All Under Heaven." Because of its special place in the universe, ancient Chinese considers itself as *the Middle Kingdom*, which "inspires and uplifts the rest of humanity."

This concept of the world sees China as the sole civilization, beyond which are barbarians who are their vassals. China occupies the apex of the universal hierarchy with nothing to equal it. It considers itself as a self-sufficient civilization in need of nothing outside its borders. For what can barbarians offer that is worth more than what the Middle Kingdom has? This is in contrast with the Westphalian Western view of statehood, wherein states recognize each other and recognize the rights of its leaders to rule their own territories, free from outside interference.²

Moreover, China's Emperor was treated as "a figure of cosmic dimensions and the linchpin between the human and the divine," whose purview is not just China, but "All Under Heaven." He considers other monarchs not as fellow sovereign "but earnest pupils in the art of governance, striving towards civilization."

Therefore, China conceives its relationship with others as tributary, wherein foreign societies or barbarians were given the opportunity to pay tribute and recognize China's special place and affirm their own assigned place in the universal hierarchy. Part of the tribute ceremony is the "kowtow" or kneeling and touching one's head to the ground to acknowledge the Emperor's superior authority. "But the kowtow was symbolically voluntary: it was the representative deference of a people that had been not so much conquered as awed."

This brings us to an important aspect of China's relations with the barbarians; which is that it never sought to export its political system nor venture into expansive campaigns to convert them into its way of thinking. Instead, it sought to induce respect by dominating psychologically through its achievements and its conduct.

China's wealth and expanse under the Qing was great that it attracted the empires of Europe. Beginning in the 17th century European traders increased in the southeast China coast. These Europeans were considered as "tribute envoys" or "barbarian merchants." Their "access to the Chinese market was strictly limited to a tightly regulated seasonal trade at Guangzhou (then known as Canton)," requiring them to sail home in winter. They were not permitted to venture further into China, disallowed to learn the Chinese language, nor allowed to purchase books on Chinese culture and history.³

¹ Kissinger, H. (2014) *World Order* (UK: Penguin Random House)

² McGrew, A. (2014) 'Globalization and global politics' in Baylis, J., Smith, S., and Owens, P. (eds), *The Globalization of World Politics* (Oxford: Oxford University Press)

³ Kissinger, H. (2011) *On China* (New York: The Penguin Press)

In the Chinese view, the Emperor was benevolent enough to allow the Europeans to partake in the Chinese market; particularly allowing their acquisition of highly coveted tea, silk, lacquerware, and rhubarb. But free trade, resident embassies, and sovereign equality were concepts alien to China.⁴

The Europeans accepted the role that China assigned to them until they grew in wealth and power; and became more confident in asserting their demands and convictions.

In 1793-94, Great Britain sent an envoy to China in the person of Lord George Macartney to propose free trade and establish reciprocal resident embassies in Beijing and London. Lord Macartney “brought with him numerous examples of British scientific and industrial prowess” to show the benefits of trading with Britain.⁵

He didn’t kowtow to the Emperor, preferring instead to kneel on one knee, the same courtesy he afforded to his own monarch. The Chinese Emperor considered his gifts as tribute as stated in his edict to King George III:

[S]trange and costly objects do not interest me. If I have commanded that the tribute offerings sent by you, O King, are to be accepted, this was solely in consideration for the spirit which prompted you to dispatch them from afar... As your Ambassador can see for himself, we possess all things.⁶

Needless to say, the mission was a failure. The second mission also failed, with the envoy not even granted an audience with the Emperor, because he didn’t want to kowtow. The mission after that also failed. In the end, the British resorted to trading in opium, which the Chinese highly coveted, and then to using force.

A Century of Humiliation⁷

The Europeans’ endeavor to integrate China into the Westphalian system of international order by pressuring them to establish free trade and cultivate diplomatic ties with the rest of the world was seen by China not as a process of enlightenment, as intended by the Europeans, but as an attack on their civilization. To the Chinese, treating these barbarians as equals was tantamount to surrendering their unique place in the universal hierarchy. The World Order that the Europeans wish to impose is incompatible with the Chinese’s.

The Chinese resisted, however, their military cannot compete with those of the Europeans. China had “neglected its military technology partly because it had been unchallenged for so long but largely because of the low status of the military in China’s Confucian social hierarchy...” Therefore, after being overwhelmed by the British in naval engagements in two opium wars, the Chinese conceded to their demands and more; ceding Hong Kong and allowing greater access to Chinese market.

This was, of course, only the beginning of China’s humiliation as other European powers and Japan utilized its military and diplomatic prowess to China’s detriment. This century saw the end of the Imperial throne, greater access by foreign powers to China’s ports and market, payment of large amounts of reparations for losses in wars, loss of influence in neighboring countries such as Korea and Vietnam, and loss of territory to foreign powers. Perhaps, the most traumatic of all was the Japanese invasion and occupation of China during World War II.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Kissinger, H. (2014) *World Order* (UK: Penguin Random House)

Apart from the loss of territory and the suffering of its people under foreign occupation, the greatest humiliation that affects the psyche of past and future generations of Chinese is having lost their unique place in the universe. The Qing court didn't just lose the mandate of heaven, from which they draw authority to rule "All Under Heaven"; the world the Chinese knew was overturned and replaced with something that has no special place for them.

A Communist State

On October 1, 1949, the communists, led by Mao Zedong, established the People's Republic of China. From the very beginning, Mao overemphasized commitment to the Communist ideology, which envisions a classless society. He wished to prevent a revisionism of their revolution, wherein the Communist party merely replaces the system that they toppled. He avoided following Russia's lead which saw the transformation of the revolution into a hierarchical system where Party leaders occupied the position formerly held by the elites.

As such, Mao pursued a "continuous revolution" whereby China underwent a purification and dismantling of the established concepts of domestic and international order. This includes rejecting both Western democratic principles and Soviet leadership of the Communist world; and dismantling the legacy of the Chinese past.⁸

He believed that society cannot be passive for long because this would lead to counter-revolutions and revisionism. In a letter to his wife at the beginning of the Cultural Revolution (1966), he stated:

The situation changes from a great upheaval to a great peace once every seven or eight years. Ghosts and monsters jump out by themselves.... Our current task is to sweep out the Rightists in all the Party and throughout the country. We shall launch another movement for sweeping up the ghosts and monsters after seven or eight years, and will launch more of this movement later.⁹

Among the upheavals that Mao initiated were: the Hundred Flowers Campaign in 1956 which invited public debate but saw the party turning on those intellectuals who practiced it; the Great Leap Forward in 1958, designed to catch up with the West industrially, but which led to a great famine; and the Cultural Revolution in 1966, which saw a generation of leaders, professors, and diplomats sent to the countryside to work on farms and learn from the masses.¹⁰

Yet, in this conception of the Communist revolution, Mao always considered his revolution as largely Sinocentric. Where Lenin and Trotsky viewed their revolution as triggering a worldwide Communist revolution, China's revolution tend to focus on its own society. He acknowledged that China's revolution might have an impact on the world, but it is "through the efforts and sacrifice and example of the Chinese people."¹¹

Considering this, one may find a resonance of the Middle Kingdom, whereby the Chinese communist revolution is self-sustaining and not part of the world revolution of the proletariat. It is unique and intrinsically Chinese, that rejects the institutions and practices exemplified by the Soviets, and that is formed out of the struggle and experience of the Chinese people.

However, the chaos of the Cultural Revolution devastated all Chinese, left the economy in ruins, and destroyed the party's credibility. Deng Xiaoping, who became the paramount leader two years after Mao's death, reversed the Cultural Revolution and instead, pursued a

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Kissinger, H. (2011) *On China*

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ Ibid.

“socialism with Chinese characteristics.¹²” He led the opening of the Chinese economy and slowly rebuilt the credibility of the party with its people by lifting millions of Chinese from poverty.

This transformation of the Chinese economy only became possible with its engagement with the world. Of course, it was ambivalent in accepting and participating in the international system, recalling the manner by which it was forced to open up to trade in the past. In its participation in the international market economy, China begrudgingly adhered to the rules of the prevailing system as a matter of prudence, even though they had no part in making it. But they expect that as they grow wealthier and stronger, “the international order [will] evolve in a way that enables China to become centrally involved in further international rule making, even to the point of revising some of the rules that prevail.¹³”

China as leader of the developing world¹⁴

Apart from being a Communist country, China also saw itself as a developing country. Prior to opening up its economy, China was poor. Their poverty was worsened by policies such as the Great Leap Forward and the Cultural Revolution. In addition, during the Cold War, the Communist party defined China's position as being with the exploited nations of the Third World; prone to being victims of “great-power chauvinism and superpower bullying.” For the Communist party, China was just as vulnerable as the rest of the developing world to domination. In fact, it shares a history with most of the Third World countries of being a country that has been conquered and divided.

Now, after overthrowing its imperial oppressors and uniting China, it has positioned itself as the leader of the developing world. Even with its economic miracle, China still sees itself as the champion of the developing world.

When China engaged in trade, the US expected it to gradually liberalize and democratize. But China stubbornly refused to accompany their economic liberalization with political liberalization.¹⁵ It is important to note that despite the lack of the rule of law and a democratic government, institutions understood to be relevant in maintaining the functioning of a free market, China continued to grow economically.¹⁶

The Chinese Communist Party will not surrender their power by democratizing. As such, we see the party revising certain principles of international order to justify their continued role in the society. An example of which is the “socialism with Chinese characteristics” where they revised the socialist model propagated by the Communist party to accommodate market reforms that will benefit the people.

The party consistently emphasized China's uniqueness, harking to the days of the self-sustaining Middle Kingdom, and rejected the preconceived notions of the West to democratize; which they view as a threat to their power and significant place in Chinese society.

What reinforced this notion is the Tiananmen Square Massacre of 1989. A result of Deng's market liberalization was not only the remarkable growth of the economy, but also the exposure of many Chinese to foreign ideas and influences. Among these is the idea of democracy as a

¹² Griffiths, J. (2016), ‘How the Cultural Revolution Changed China Forever’ *CNN* [Online] 17 May. <https://edition.cnn.com/2016/05/12/asia/china-cultural-revolution-dikotter/index.html> [Accessed: 18 February 2018].

¹³ Kissinger, H. (2014) *World Order*

¹⁴ Kelly, D. (2018) ‘Seven Chinas’ *CSIS* [Online] https://csis-prod.s3.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/publication/180205_Kelly_SevenChinasAPolicyFramework_Web.pdf?6WseCRmF93b8k1MpBeuo_f9idbMzJpaB [Accessed: 8 February 2018].

¹⁵ Breslin, S. (2009) ‘Understanding China's regional rise: interpretations, identities and implications’ *International Affairs* (85: 4), pp. 817-835

¹⁶ Wang, L. and Zheng, J. (2012) ‘China's rise as a new paradigm in the world economy: preliminaries’ *Journal of Chinese Economic and Business Studies* (10:4), pp. 301-312

form of government. The death of a pro-democracy party leader sparked massive protests in Tiananmen Square in Beijing and several other cities across China. The Communist party, fearing a loss of power, used force to disperse the protesters resulting in the deaths of thousands of Chinese.¹⁷ Thus, it may be surmised that among China's motivations in its pursuit of domestic and foreign policy is the preservation of power of the Chinese Communist Party.

A Rising Power

In order to fully grasp the idea of China as a rising power, there is a need to contextualize its rise amidst the competing and often conflicting narratives of its identity. For instance, how does the legacy of imperial China or the Middle Kingdom, blend with the ideals of the communist revolution? Or how does the century of humiliation factor into its narrative of a rising power?

For all this, we should consider the Communist party as the linchpin that holds all these narratives together. As the inheritor of the Middle Kingdom, China continues to see itself as a self-sufficient civilization, whose social and political development is unique in itself. And the Communist party constantly reinforces this notion to reject Western ideas that threaten their hold on power, such as democracy, rule of law, and human rights.

This notion is supported by China's economic miracle wherein it was able to achieve high levels of growth even without the democratic institutions, which Western conventional wisdom considers as prerequisites for economic development. In the end, China developed a unique liberal market-authoritarian model that is being copied by authoritarian Third World countries.¹⁸

This blends well with the narrative that China survived as a Communist state because it didn't follow the development models of both the Westerners and the Soviets, but instead, pursued its own model of development that created wealth for its people while protecting the power of the Communist party.

This orientation has been applied in its engagement with other countries. "China has the utmost respect for state sovereignty and does not seek to impose values and policies on other countries."¹⁹ In fact, in providing loans to other countries, it purports as not attaching any conditions such as respect for human rights and democratization; in stark contrast to the practice of Western countries.

Finally, in considering how "a century of humiliation" play into China's narrative, there is still a need to consider the Middle Kingdom and Communist state narratives. The notion is not so much to avenge the century of humiliation, but serve as a lesson for the leadership to be cautious against the interference of outside forces. To recall, the Qing Imperial court fell when Western powers used force to meddle in the internal affairs of China and forced it to open to trade. Any outside interference and force within its waters may be considered an existential threat to the Communist party, the same as it was a threat to the Qing Imperial Court.

To add to this narrative is the lesson from the fate suffered by the USSR when it fell. Chinese policy-makers have become paranoid that they will suffer the same fate as the USSR. As such, they have prioritized domestic stability through economic engagement and ensured that there are no external challenges— whether political, economic, or military.²⁰

¹⁷ Encyclopædia Britannica (n.d.) 'Tiananmen Square incident' [Online] <https://www.britannica.com/event/Tiananmen-Square-incident> (Accessed: 19 February 2018).

¹⁸ Wang, L. and Zheng, J. (2012) 'China's rise as a new paradigm in the world economy: preliminaries'

¹⁹ Breslin, S. (2009) 'Understanding China's regional rise: interpretations, identities and implications'

²⁰ Ibid.

This fear manifested itself in the 1995 – 1996 Taiwan Strait crisis. Taiwan President Lee Tang-hui made a private trip to the US to attend a Cornell University reunion. During his visit, he repeatedly used the term “Republic of China on Taiwan,” which was viewed by the Chinese as a challenge to the “One China” policy. In response, China conducted missile tests and military drills near Taiwan. This intensified in the run-up to Taiwan’s first election of their president. The Chinese clearly wanted to intimidate the Taiwanese that to elect Lee would mean war. However, the Taiwanese still elected Lee as President. The US responded to China’s actions against Taiwan by deploying carrier groups and having it sail through the Taiwan Strait.²¹

For the Chinese, this highlighted their vulnerability to US military power, and raised the potential threat to the Communist party. This also showed their constraints in protecting their own interests. And this contributed to its foreign policy agenda, especially in the South China Sea.

The contemporary Chinese leadership

“Some of China’s contemporary leaders suffered grievously during the Cultural Revolution, but they now present that suffering as having given them the strength and self-discovery to steel themselves for the daunting tasks of leading another period of vast transformation.”²²

The current Chinese President, Xi Jinping, was only 13 years old when the Cultural Revolution happened. His father, who was a party official, was purged a few years earlier and was repeatedly beaten. Their home was ransacked by the Red Guards, forcing them to flee. One of his sisters died in the mayhem. He was caught, and then paraded before a crowd as an enemy of the revolution, where even his own mother was forced to denounce him in public.²³

Xi’s generation venerated Mao Zedong, but his family suffered in the violence brought by Mao’s Cultural Revolution. Yet, “[u]nlike some youths from elite backgrounds, Mr. Xi did not turn against the party or Mao, but learned to revere strict order and abhor challenges to hierarchy...”²⁴ He suffered much, but some argue that because of that Xi has formed the belief that the persecuted elites earned the right to “inherit Mao’s place at the center.”²⁵

Now, as President, he has consolidated his power. He has clamped down on corruption, though some say this was aimed against political enemies. There is also an increasing restriction on freedoms, “from rising online censorship to arrests of dissidents and human rights lawyers, leading some to describe Mr. Xi as ‘the most authoritarian leader since Chairman Mao.’”²⁶

Under his leadership, China has become more assertive on the global stage; from the South China Sea, to leadership in Climate Change, and to billions of aid to Asia and Africa.²⁷

The blending of these narratives contextualizes the rise of China: Does the rise of a Communist, non-democratic, non-conformist power pose a threat to the Western democratic, rules-based, World Order? Does China pose a threat of replacing the US as a superpower, the primary creator and guarantor of the prevailing World Order?

The short answer is NO. The power differential between the US and China is so vast that a change in a superpower is near impossible. If we consider it, the US’ defense spending is bigger than the combined spending of the next ten top military spenders in the world (China, India, Russia, Saudi Arabia, France, Germany, UK, Japan, South Korea, and Brazil). In 2019,

²¹ GlobalSecurity.org (n.d.) ‘Taiwan Strait’ [Online] https://www.globalsecurity.org/military/ops/taiwan_strait.htm (Accessed: 20 February 2018).

²² Kissinger, H. (2014) *World Order*

²³ Buckley, C. and Tatlow, D. K., (2015) ‘Cultural Revolution Shaped Xi Jinping, From Schoolboy to Survivor’ [Online] <https://www.nytimes.com/2015/09/25/world/asia/xi-jinping-china-cultural-revolution.html> (Accessed: 20 February 2018).

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ BBC (2017) ‘Profile: China’s President Xi Jinping’ [Online] <http://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-pacific-11551399> (Accessed: 21 February 2018).

²⁷ Ibid.

the US spent US\$732 billion for defense while China only spent US\$261 billion.²⁸ Not only that, but the US also has greater command of the global commons— the sea, space, and air— with its far advanced military hardware, a number of foreign military bases, and a system of alliances around the globe.²⁹

Furthermore, the World Order has been institutionalized through various international laws and international groups (i.e., the UN) that reinforces and implements those laws. “China has been more constrained by the rules of what is now a much more highly institutionalized global economy... and also by its need to keep export markets open.³⁰”

However, while these may be so, many countries believe that China is a threat. Chinese leadership were aware that their political structure and their official rhetoric (and actions) “reinforced conceptions of China as a revisionist power and fueled existing concerns about the consequences of China’s rise.³¹”

‘Acutely conscious that its rapid rise leads other countries to view it as a threat’³², ‘China’s diplomats have worked hard since the 1990s to build its reputation as a good global citizen and regional neighbor’³³ ‘in an effort to remove the distrust and sense of insecurity among China’s neighbours’.³⁴

As such, Chinese leaders have turned to the idea of “peaceful rise,” articulated during the Bo’ao Forum for Asia in 2003.³⁵ “Peaceful rise involves a two-way process in which the rising power accommodates itself to the rules and structures of international society, while at the same time other great powers accommodate some changes in those rules and structures by way of adjusting to the new disposition of power and status.³⁶”

An example of this is how China opened up to trade and development, while also establishing its own development bank (i.e., the AIIB) that attaches no conditions to loans, unlike the conditions attached to western institutions that asks borrowers to democratize and implement the rule of law.

Of course, this “peaceful rise” is just one among China’s many faces. Because while one can see the manifestations of this peaceful rise in terms of trade and economic engagement, when it comes to issues that are close to home (i.e., the South China Sea), China has a more hardline stance. This duality, though, is not unique to China, as even the US violate its own principles in pursuit of its strategic objective— such as their support to allied dictators during the Cold War.

For China, control of the South China Sea is crucial so that they may manage the entry of foreign ships, particularly the US navy, to prevent another Taiwan Strait incident that threatened their national interest (i.e., the reunification of Taiwan). But, in trying to control the sea, they have inevitably come into confrontation with the other powers in the region, as well as the US and its allies.³⁷

²⁸ Statista (2020) ‘The 15 countries with the highest military spending worldwide in 2019’ [Online] <https://www.statista.com/statistics/262742/countries-with-the-highest-military-spending/> (Accessed: 30 March 2021).

²⁹ Brooks, S. and Wohlforth, C. (2015/16) ‘The Rise and Fall of the Great Powers in the Twenty-first Century’ *International Security* (40:3), pp. 7-53

³⁰ Buzan, B. and Cox, M. (2013) ‘China and the US: Comparable Cases of ‘Peaceful Rise’?’ *The Chinese Journal of International Politics* (6:0), pp. 109-132

³¹ Breslin, S. (2009) ‘Understanding China’s regional rise: interpretations, identities and implications’

³² Shirk cited in Breslin, S. (2009)

³³ Zhang and Tang cited in Breslin, S. (2009)

³⁴ Gill and Huang cited in Breslin, S. (2009)

³⁵ Breslin, S. (2009) ‘Understanding China’s regional rise: interpretations, identities and implications’

³⁶ Buzan, B. and Cox, M. (2013) ‘China and the US: Comparable Cases of ‘Peaceful Rise’?’

³⁷ Ibid.

Control of the South China Sea may also be considered as a means to preserve the Communist party. China's rise is linked to its economic miracle, which became possible through trade. Any threat that may disrupt trade and result in economic difficulties of more than 1.3 billion Chinese threatens the position of the Communist party.

Accompanying this bid to control the South China Sea is advocating multipolarity³⁸, wherein there are several "spheres of influence" led by the strongest country— Asia would be led by China— while the US is prevented from interfering with the affairs of other regions, confining it to the Americas. This is seen as effectively ending the threat posed by the US to China.

The South China Sea

Sourced from both UNCLOS and the CIA, the BBC's (2017) map shows China's Nine-Dash Line encompassing the various 200 nautical mile EEZ of claimant countries in the South China Sea.

The South China Sea is a body of water situated in the middle of China and Southeast Asia. It is home to the Paracel Islands, the Spratly Islands, and the Scarborough Shoal, which is the subject of competing claims among China, the Philippines, and other Southeast Asian countries.

³⁸ Brooks, S. and Wohlforth, C. (2015/16) 'The Rise and Fall of the Great Powers in the Twenty-first Century'

Significance of the Region

The value of the South China Sea and the features within it lies in the maritime resources it houses. It encompasses around 3.5 million square kilometers of water³⁹, and contains an estimated “11 billion barrels of oil and 190 trillion cubic feet of natural gas in proved and probable reserves.”⁴⁰ It is also estimated to provide 16.6 million tons of fish annually, providing employment for around 3.7 million people.⁴¹ Furthermore, “[o]ver 40,000 ships pass through the South China Sea every year, constituting around 40 per cent of global sea trade.”⁴² These resources and shipping lanes have made the disputes in the area a pressing security concern.

During World War II, Japan used Itu Aba [now occupied by Taiwan⁴³] as a staging area to occupy the Philippines.⁴⁴ Few believe, though, that China will invade the Philippines from its occupied islands in the Spratly’s.⁴⁵ It must be noted that the Philippines is an ally of the US, who would come to its aid when attacked. However, China’s newly reclaimed features with military installations in the Spratly Islands may be considered as bases of operations for further encroachment into Philippine territory and establishing control over the area, limiting the passage of ships and small vessels (oftentimes fishing vessels).

Apparently, the most immediate cause of conflict and small clashes between the Philippines and China is due to fishing activities. In fact, the Philippines routinely arrests Chinese fishermen in *Kalayaan*⁴⁶ to assert its sovereignty by implementing its laws.⁴⁷ However, China has effectively organized fishing fleets, subsidized its fishermen to fish in disputed waters, and deployed the Chinese Coast Guard to support them and counter Philippine maritime law enforcement vessels.⁴⁸ These actions not only showed China’s control over the area, but also effectively violated the Philippines’ fishing rights within its exclusive economic zone.⁴⁹

On oil and gas, the Philippines created the Western Command to defend *Kalayaan*. The underlying motivation was the discovery of oil in the Reed Bank, midway between Palawan and *Kalayaan*.⁵⁰ In 1994, the Philippines permitted a US oil company, Vaalco, and its Philippine subsidiary Alcorn, to conduct oil exploration near the Reed Bank; which the Chinese protested.⁵¹

³⁹ Morton, K. (2016) ‘China’s ambition in the South China Sea: is a legitimate maritime order possible?’ *International Affairs* (92:4), pp. 909-940

⁴⁰ U.S. Energy Information Administration (2013) ‘South China Sea’ [Online] <https://www.eia.gov/beta/international/regions-topics.cfm?RegionTopicID=SCS> (Accessed: 5 August 2017).

⁴¹ Bale, R. (2016) ‘One of the World’s Biggest Fisheries Is on the Verge of Collapse’ [Online] <http://news.nationalgeographic.com/2016/08/wildlife-south-china-sea-overfishing-threatens-collapse/> (Accessed: 5 August 2017).

⁴² Morton, K. (2016) ‘China’s ambition in the South China Sea: is a legitimate maritime order possible?’

⁴³ Vuving, A.L. (2016) ‘South China Sea: Who Occupies What in the Spratlys?’ [Online] <http://thediplomat.com/2016/05/south-china-sea-who-claims-what-in-the-spratlys/> (Accessed: 5 August 2017).

⁴⁴ Lim, B.O. (2000) ‘Tempest over the South China Sea: The Chinese perspective on the Spratlys’ *Asian Studies* (36:2), pp. 69-132

⁴⁵ Zha, D. and Valencia, M.J. (2001) ‘Mischief Reef: Geopolitics and Implications’ *Journal of Contemporary Asia* (31:1), pp. 86-103

⁴⁶ Named by the Philippines as the Kalayaan Island Group, it is the portion of the Spratly Islands claimed by the Philippines.
⁴⁷ Ibid.

⁴⁸ Bale, R. (2016) ‘One of the World’s Biggest Fisheries Is on the Verge of Collapse’

⁴⁹ Perlez, J. (2016) ‘Tribunal Rejects Beijing’s Claims in South China Sea’ [Online] <https://www.nytimes.com/2016/07/13/world/asia/south-china-sea-hague-ruling-philippines.html> (Accessed: 30 June 2017).

⁵⁰ Lim, B.O. (2000) ‘Tempest over the South China Sea: The Chinese perspective on the Spratlys’

⁵¹ Storey, I.J. (1999) ‘Creeping Assertiveness: China, the Philippines and the South China Sea Dispute’ *Contemporary Southeast Asia* (21:1), pp. 95-118

Oil and natural gas is as much a concern of China as it is of the Philippines that it even proposed the idea of joint exploration. In 2004, the Philippines and China, through the Philippine National Oil Company (PNOC) and China National Offshore Oil Corporation (CNOOC), agreed to conduct seismic surveys in the South China Sea.⁵²

However, while natural resources determine the strategic importance of the South China Sea for a small state like the Philippines, for a great power like China, it is more than just that.

China is worried that US policy in Asia is designed to contain China. The bulk of the global trade that pass through the South China Sea has benefitted China's economy and increased its wealth. Moreover, Taiwan continues to enjoy the support of the US, despite China's claim towards it. Furthermore, the US has significant military deployment in Japan and South Korea and is an ally of many Asian nations. China fears of a possible strategic blockade by the US and its allies that would affect its trade and allow their forces to enter the Taiwan Strait and its near seas.⁵³

As such, China prioritized an "offshore defence' strategy based upon anti-access and area denial (A2/AD)" to defend against foreign forces and prevent their control of the waters and airspace in the region.⁵⁴ China seeks to limit US influence and involvement in Asia, envisioning a regional order where China is preponderant and the US is confined to the Americas.

Competing claims between China and the Philippines

China claims almost all of the South China Sea, along with the islands, cays, reefs, atolls, rocks, shoals, sand bars, coral reefs, and other features within it. The subject of disputes between the Philippines and China is the Scarborough Shoal and the largest group of islands, the Spratly Islands.⁵⁵

China bases its claims on historic rights, noting that it discovered and occupied islands in the South China Sea since the Han Dynasty (206 B.C. to 220 A.D.).⁵⁶ In 1992, China's National People's Congress passed the territorial law, which converted the South China Sea into its internal waters, seeking to control and manage the passage of all vessels in the area.⁵⁷ The claim was emphasized with the UN in 2009 through a *note verable*⁵⁸ containing a map with a "nine-dash line" that delineates the boundaries of China's jurisdiction in the South China Sea. The origin of this nine-dash line is a map drafted in the 1930s by a mid-ranking official of the Republic of China's Land and Water Maps Inspection Committee, the purpose of which was merely to identify the islands in the South China Sea, and not to declare its claims.⁵⁹

During the Sino-Japanese War of 1894 and well into World War II, Japan claimed the features in the South China Sea, even driving away some Chinese who stayed in the Spratly Islands. Upon its surrender in 1945, Japan accepted the conditions of the Potsdam Proclamation, including limiting Japanese sovereignty to the territory of Japan and its adjacent minor islands.

⁵² Storey, I. (2008) 'Conflict in the South China Sea: China's Relations with Vietnam and the Philippines', *The Asia-Pacific Journal* (6:4), pp. 1-13

⁵³ Morton, K. (2016) 'China's ambition in the South China Sea: is a legitimate maritime order possible?' *International Affairs* (92:4), pp. 909-940

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Lim, B.O. (2000) 'Tempest over the South China Sea: The Chinese perspective on the Spratlys'

⁵⁶ Storey, I.J. (1999) 'Creeping Assertiveness: China, the Philippines and the South China Sea Dispute'

⁵⁷ Buszynski, L. (2003) 'ASEAN, the Declaration on Conduct, and the South China Sea' *Contemporary Southeast Asia* (25:3), pp. 343-362

⁵⁸ The *note verbale* was sent to the UN in response to Malaysia and Vietnam's joint submission in 2009 to the Commission on the Outer Limits of the Continental Shelf, in compliance with the deadline of the UNCLOS for submission of its claims and jurisdiction in their waters (Morton, 2016: 919).

⁵⁹ Morton, K. (2016) 'China's ambition in the South China Sea: is a legitimate maritime order possible?'

In the San Francisco Peace Treaty of 1951, Japan renounced sovereignty over the islands in the South China Sea but it did not specifically return these to China. Probably because it wasn't determined yet whether the Communists (China) or Nationalists (Taiwan) represented China. Also, both parties were not included in the conference that decided the treaty as the US and USSR can't agree on which government represented China.⁶⁰

However, this has not stopped the People's Republic of China (communist China) from asserting its claims in the South China Sea, including in the Spratly Islands. China occupies seven features, all of which has been reclaimed and turned into artificial islands with military installations. These features are: Subi Reef, Gaven Reef, Hughes Reef, Johnson South Reef, Fiery Cross Reef, Cuarteron Reef, and Mischief Reef

On the other hand, the Philippines' claim date back to 1956 when Tomas Cloma, founder of the Philippine Maritime Institute, claimed ownership of more than thirty features in the Spratly Islands on the basis of discovery and occupation. In 1974, he transferred all rights and interests over the features to the Republic of the Philippines.⁶¹

From 1978 to 1979, then-President Marcos issued Presidential Decrees which claimed the features as Philippine territory, premised on the notion that these features were not owned, considering that the 1951 San Francisco Peace Treaty did not give the title to the islands to any specific country. The Presidential Decrees also clarified that the Philippines was not claiming the entire Spratly Islands but only a portion of it, which the Philippines called the *Kalayaan Island Group*.⁶² Furthermore, it may be noted that Spratly Islands is only about 250 miles from the Philippine province of Palawan, compared to 550 miles from the Chinese province of Hainan Island.⁶³

The Philippines' claims were registered with the UN in 1980.⁶⁴ Also, the Western Command was established in Palawan with the purpose of defending *Kalayaan*, while an airstrip was built on Pagasa Island, the largest island in *Kalayaan*⁶⁵, where a settlement with active voters was organized under the jurisdiction of the province of Palawan.⁶⁶

In 2012, then-President Benigno Simeon Aquino III, issued Administrative Order No. 29, which declared the maritime areas on the western side of the Philippines as the West Philippine Sea. These include the Luzon Sea as well as the waters around, within and adjacent to the Kalayaan Island Group and Bajo De Masinloc, also known as Scarborough Shoal.⁶⁷

The Philippines holds nine features in the South China Sea: Northeast Cay, Thitu Island (Pagasa), Loaita Cay, Loaita Island, West York Island, Flat Island, Nanshan Island, Second Thomas Shoal, and Commodore Reef. Another feature, which is not part of *Kalayaan*, is the Scarborough Shoal (Bajo de Masinloc). It is around 136 miles away from the Philippines' northern province of Zambales, and is around 497 miles southeast of Hong Kong.⁶⁸

⁶⁰ Lim, B.O. (2000) 'Tempest over the South China Sea: The Chinese perspective on the Spratlys'

⁶¹ Cariño, T.C. (1995-1996) 'Philippine-China relations in the post-Cold War era' *Asian Studies* (31-32:0), pp. 50-63

⁶² Lim, B.O. (2000) 'Tempest over the South China Sea: The Chinese perspective on the Spratlys'

⁶³ Cariño, T.C. (1995-1996) 'Philippine-China relations in the post-Cold War era'

⁶⁴ Ibid.

⁶⁵ Lim, B.O. (2000) 'Tempest over the South China Sea: The Chinese perspective on the Spratlys'

⁶⁶ Cariño, T.C. (1995-1996) 'Philippine-China relations in the post-Cold War era'

⁶⁷ Official Gazette (2012) 'Administrative Order No. 29, s. 2012' [Online]

<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2012/09/05/administrative-order-no-29-s-2012/> (Accessed: 30 March 2021)

⁶⁸ Inquirer (2012) 'Scarborough shoal standoff: A timeline' [Online] <http://globalnation.inquirer.net/36003/scarborough-shoal-standoff-a-historical-timeline> (Accessed: 30 June 2017).

UNCLOS and the Philippines' Arbitral Win

The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) is an international treaty that was adopted in 1982, which concerns the territorial sea and the contiguous zone; the continental shelf; the high seas; and fishing and conservation of living resources on the high seas.⁶⁹ Both China and the Philippines are signatories to the UNCLOS.

One of the most revolutionary features of UNCLOS is the exclusive economic zone (EEZ), which sets it at 200 nautical miles from a country's shore, in which it has jurisdiction "to exploit, develop, manage, and conserve all resources – fish or oil, gas or gravel, nodules or Sulphur – to be found in the waters, on the ocean floor and in the subsoil of an area..."⁷⁰

In 2016, with the Philippines' arbitral win against China, the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea (ITLOS) found that China's Nine-Dash Line was incompatible with the provisions of UNCLOS, and that its claim to "historic rights" were extinguished when UNCLOS came into effect.⁷¹

The Tribunal also found that China's harassment of Philippine fishermen and surveillance vessels, its encroachment on Philippine waters (EEZ), its support for Chinese fishermen to operate in Philippine waters, and its land reclamations; violated the Philippines' sovereign rights with respect to its EEZ.⁷²

Of course, while the Philippines succeeded in utilizing international law, the enforcement of the ruling is another matter, especially now that the Duterte administration decided to have closer ties with Beijing over the country's traditional ally, the US. Moreover, it seems quite daunting to assert the rights of a small state like the Philippines against a great power like China.

The Options of Small States

Small states, like the Philippines, may be weak but they are not helpless. In the current World Order, small states are allied with one great power or another. They may use these alliances in countering threats from another great power state. Furthermore, current international rules, norms, and laws would constrain the actions of threatening power from outright aggression. These are options available to small states should they decide to stand up to threatening great powers.

An Argument for Balancing

There are two actions that a state can do when threatened; they could either balance or bandwagon. Balancing is forming alliances and/or turning to international institutions to deter a threatening state; while bandwagoning is aligning with the threatening power.⁷³

There are two forms of balancing. One is hard balancing, which is the more traditional and military form of balancing "based on countervailing alliances and arms buildups..."⁷⁴ The other is soft balancing, which involves the use of "international institutions, economic statecraft, and

⁶⁹ United Nations (1998) 'The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (A historical perspective)' [Online] https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/convention_historical_perspective.htm (Accessed: 29 April 2019).

⁷⁰ Ibid.

⁷¹ Permanent Court of Arbitration (2016) 'Press Release: The South China Sea Arbitration'

⁷² Ibid.

⁷³ Walt, S.M. (1987) *The Origins of Alliances*, Ithaca: Cornell University Press.

⁷⁴ Paul, T.V. (2005) 'Soft Balancing in the Age of U.S. Primacy' *International Security* (30:1), pp. 46-71

diplomatic arrangements...” as well as other non-military tools in constraining, if not, deterring threats from great powers.⁷⁵

Several scholars argue that it is preferable to balance against a threatening power than to bandwagon with it because of the following:⁷⁶

- Balancing would allow a state greater freedom of action than being subordinated to a great power state
- A state cannot simply rely on the continued benevolence of a great power
- States place their survival and national interest at risk if they fail to counter a threatening power before it becomes too strong to oppose⁷⁷

Small states do not have to rely on their own capability to balance against a threatening power. They may also utilize their alliances with other great powers to balance. For instance, the Philippines may use its alliance with the US and Japan to balance against a threatening China. Aside from the alliance system, another avenue available to small states are international institutions. Small states turn to these institutions for recourse and to limit the unilateralism of the threatening great power.⁷⁸

We are therefore dealing with two broad types of balancing: balancing conducted by military means for specific military ends and balancing conducted by political means directed at an opponent's image and legitimacy. Common to both types, however, is the desire to acquire support from others in response to an external threat.⁷⁹

If balancing should be the preferred response, why is bandwagoning an option? States bandwagon when they are vulnerable and when their allies are unavailable.⁸⁰ However, no small state exist in isolation from the rest of the world that a threat against it will go unnoticed. Most small state is an ally of a great power, a member of a regional grouping or regional organization, or both. In addition, small states belong to an international community of nations; the United Nations (UN). Should a great power threaten the security of a small state, it shall also contend with that small state's great power ally; the regional grouping it belongs to; and the rules and norms enshrined in international institutions.

For instance, when China threatened the security of the Philippines on the South China Sea issue, it was not confined to a bilateral issue. The US and the ASEAN got involved in balancing China's assertiveness. Also, the Philippines sought recourse from the Permanent Court of Arbitration (PCA) in constraining and delegitimizing China's actions in the South China Sea.

The power of institutions and regional groupings do not lie in the force of numbers alone. It would be wrong to simply assume that one can turn to international institutions and regional groupings because of the quantity of the members and the attendant capability of each of those members. In fact, the capabilities of member states can't be brought to bear in a concerted action against a threatening state, unless that is part of the agreement such as with NATO or legally sanctioned as determined in its proceedings. The power of these institutions lie in the norms enshrined in them and how they act in concerted effort to safeguard and protect these norms, most especially those that promote sovereignty and self-determination. These concerted efforts need not be military in nature, there are other tools available such as sanctions or international condemnation and isolation.

⁷⁵ Pape, R.A. (2005) 'Soft Balancing against the United States', *International Security* (30:1), pp. 7-45

⁷⁶ Walt, S.M. (1985) 'Alliance Formation and the Balance of World Power' *International Security* (9:4), pp. 3-43

⁷⁷ Walt, S.M. (1987) *The Origins of Alliances*, Ithaca: Cornell University Press.

⁷⁸ Long, T. (2016) 'Small States, Great Power? Gaining Influence Through Intrinsic, Derivative, and Collective Power'

⁷⁹ Walt, S.M. (1987) *The Origins of Alliances*

⁸⁰ Walt, S.M. (1985) 'Alliance Formation and the Balance of World Power'

Philippine History of Balancing Against China

1994/ 1995 Mischief Reef Occupation – Engaging ASEAN and the US to Check China

A series of significant and relevant events occurred prior to the Mischief Reef incident. In 1991, the Philippines terminated the US leases over Clark Air Force Base and Subic Bay Naval Base, two of the US' largest overseas bases at the time. Many Filipino nationalists won the argument with political leaders on the non-necessity of US bases considering the fall of the Soviet Union and the lack of a serious external threat. Moreover, since the US provided a security blanket to the Philippines, it has neglected to modernize its air force and navy. Furthermore, the political leaders diverted funds away from defense to social welfare and economic projects thinking that the Philippines does not face any external threat.⁸¹

The developments in the Philippines in 1991 to 1992 coincided with China's passage of the Law on Territorial Sea and Contiguous Zones, where China reiterated its claims over the features in the South China Sea. In addition, China continued to occupy reefs claimed by Vietnam and even announced the awarding of an oil exploration contract to an American company, Crestone. Although Vietnam then was not yet a member of ASEAN, China's actions nonetheless prompted the then-six ASEAN members to issue the Manila Declaration in 1992, which called on all claimants "to exercise restraint in the pursuit of their claims and to explore cooperative ventures as a means of preventing conflict."⁸²

However, in early 1995, the Philippines discovered that China occupied and built structures on Mischief Reef, which is 135 nautical miles from the Philippine province of Palawan, well within its 200-mile EEZ.⁸³ Investigations by the Philippine military revealed that China had been secretly building structures on Mischief Reef since late 1994.⁸⁴ It was the first time that China came into conflict with a member of ASEAN, and the first conflict between China and the Philippines. Previously, the conflict in the South China Sea was predominantly between China and Vietnam.⁸⁵

In response to China's "occupation", the Philippine Congress introduced a fifteen-year US\$12.6 billion defense modernization bill⁸⁶, originally outlined by then-President Ramos in 1989. Moreover, the Philippines engaged in diplomatic offensives against China, with Ramos condemning the construction as violating the spirit of the Manila Declaration and inconsistent with international law.⁸⁷ In May 1995, the Philippine Navy ferried journalists near Mischief Reef and subsequently flew them over outposts to gain support from the international community.⁸⁸

The Philippines also successfully gathered ASEAN's support, and during the first China-ASEAN Forum in April 1995, ASEAN told China that its actions in the South China Sea negatively affected regional stability and that the issue should be settled peacefully. ASEAN also raised the South China Sea disputes with China during the ASEAN Regional Forum in

⁸¹ Storey, I.J. (1999) 'Creeping Assertiveness: China, the Philippines and the South China Sea Dispute'

⁸² San Pablo-Baviera, A. (2002) 'The China Challenge to ASEAN Solidarity: The Case of the South China Sea Disputes' *Asian Studies* (38:2), pp. 93-120

⁸³ San Pablo-Baviera, A. (2002) 'The China Challenge to ASEAN Solidarity: The Case of the South China Sea Disputes'

⁸⁴ Lim, B.O. (2000) 'Tempest over the South China Sea: The Chinese perspective on the Spratlys'

⁸⁵ Zha, D. and Valencia, M.J. (2001) 'Mischief Reef: Geopolitics and Implications'

⁸⁶ Although an ambitious spending program was set by law, no funds were released for the program from 1997 – 1999 due to the Asian financial crisis, the diversion of funds for the 1998 National Elections, and the eruption of hostilities in Southern Philippines (Office of the President of the Philippines, 2015).

⁸⁷ Storey, I.J. (1999) 'Creeping Assertiveness: China, the Philippines and the South China Sea Dispute'

⁸⁸ Lim, B.O. (2000) 'Tempest over the South China Sea: The Chinese perspective on the Spratlys'

August 1995, and in the face of a united opposition, China stated that it was willing to resolve its disputes with other claimants based on international law, the UNCLOS.⁸⁹

The international support, and pressure from ASEAN contributed to a bilateral agreement between the Philippines and China to abide by certain principles for a code of conduct, which included an agreement that the dispute should not affect their overall diplomatic relations, that it be settled in a peaceful and friendly manner, and in accordance with UNCLOS. Both parties also agreed to undertake confidence-building measures, to refrain from the use of force, and to cooperate for the protection and conservation of maritime resources.⁹⁰

A point must be emphasized here, that while the Philippines engaged ASEAN on the South China Sea dispute, it did not seek support for its claims. Instead, the Philippines sought support to encourage all claimants to abide by established rules and norms of peaceful settlement of disputes and avoiding the use of force.

And yet, while diplomatically, the Philippines seem to be winning, it still does not have physical possession of the Mischief Reef. “Manila hoped that by pursuing negotiations, Beijing would dismantle the structures,”⁹¹ but it was not so. Instead, the Philippines continued to apprehend Chinese poachers operating in the Spratly Islands and Scarborough Shoal⁹²; and destroy Chinese boundary markers. While both parties managed to avoid escalation to armed conflict, the Mischief Reef continue to be under Chinese possession.⁹³

The issue worsened in October 1998 when the Chinese reinforced and placed a more permanent structure in the Mischief Reef, with “emerging military facility” equipped with helipads, gun emplacement platforms, and radar. This time, though, the Philippines was unsuccessful in rallying ASEAN unified support in publicly condemning China, who assisted some of its members in the wake of the Asian financial crisis.⁹⁴ Though Chinese actions were not condemned, ASEAN reasserted the principles of peaceful settlement of disputes in accordance with international law.

More importantly, the Philippines brought the US military presence back through the Visiting Forces Agreement (VFA). Ratified by the Philippine Senate in 1999, Philippine leaders saw the VFA as deterring Chinese actions in the Spratly Islands, through military and naval exercises. However, the Americans constantly noted that Philippine claims in the Spratly Islands is not covered by their Mutual Defense Treaty.⁹⁵ The US also asserted and reinforced international rules and norms, including the freedom of navigation, in discussions on the South China Sea.⁹⁶

The involvement of the US was a grave concern for China.

[T]he Chinese became aware of the risks of pushing ASEAN countries militarily closer to the U.S. which would result in greater access to the region’s port facilities for the American navy and strengthened military cooperation. Enhanced U.S. access to ASEAN would then assist the implementation of U.S. military strategy in relation to the Taiwan issue providing the American navy with a position to counter a Chinese naval blockade of the island.⁹⁷

⁸⁹ Storey, I.J. (1999) 'Creeping Assertiveness: China, the Philippines and the South China Sea Dispute'

⁹⁰ San Pablo-Baviera, A. (2002) 'The China Challenge to ASEAN Solidarity: The Case of the South China Sea Disputes'

⁹¹ Storey, I.J. (1999) 'Creeping Assertiveness: China, the Philippines and the South China Sea Dispute'

⁹² San Pablo-Baviera, A. (2002) 'The China Challenge to ASEAN Solidarity: The Case of the South China Sea Disputes'

⁹³ Zha, D. and Valencia, M.J. (2001) 'Mischief Reef: Geopolitics and Implications'

⁹⁴ San Pablo-Baviera, A. (2002) 'The China Challenge to ASEAN Solidarity: The Case of the South China Sea Disputes'

⁹⁵ Lim, B.O. (2000) 'Tempest over the South China Sea: The Chinese perspective on the Spratlys'

⁹⁶ Storey, I.J. (1999) 'Creeping Assertiveness: China, the Philippines and the South China Sea Dispute'

⁹⁷ Buszynski, L. (2003) 'ASEAN, the Declaration on Conduct, and the South China Sea'

US involvement and the ASEAN's assertion of norms of peaceful settlement of disputes in accordance with international law encouraged China to engage ASEAN for a Code of Conduct in the South China Sea (COC), which was endorsed by ASEAN foreign ministers back in 1996, using the Philippines-China 1995 code as model. Moreover, China saw it as an opportunity to create rules that would limit US military presence in the region.⁹⁸ Finally, China saw the strategic value of ASEAN, as the preponderant regional grouping that may be engaged to balance and/or constrain US military presence and actions in the region.⁹⁹

The Philippines considers ASEAN as a pillar of its foreign policy, particularly in managing territorial disputes with China. As such, it has actively engaged and sought support from ASEAN in constraining China's unilateral actions in the South China Sea. And while ASEAN will not step in to settle disputes, it will take a stand to keep the region peaceful.¹⁰⁰ ASEAN's constant assertion on the peaceful settlement of disputes as well as adherence to international law was to preserve regional peace and stability.

In November 2002, ASEAN and China signed a non-legally binding Declaration on the Conduct of Parties in the South China Sea (DOC), which although not the much sought after COC, was a welcome development among ASEAN because China signed a multilateral declaration over the South China Sea issue.¹⁰¹

The DOC includes ASEAN's assertion for: (1) a commitment to the freedom of navigation and overflight in the South China Sea; (2) peaceful settlement of disputes, without resorting to force, and engaging in friendly consultations and negotiations; and (3) exercising self-restraint by all parties and avoiding actions that would "complicate or escalate disputes and affect peace and stability including, among others, refraining from action of inhabiting on the presently uninhabited islands, reefs, shoals, cays, and other features and to handle their differences in a constructive manner."¹⁰²

Cooperation through JMSU – A Costly Engagement

The change in Philippine policy towards China and the South China Sea came on the back of significant developments domestically and internationally. China signed the DOC with ASEAN in 2002. There was a leadership change in the Philippines, with President Arroyo taking over from ousted President Estrada in 2001. Arroyo highlighted economic recovery as her goal and sought to accomplish this by engaging China economically. In fact, Philippines-China relations was described to have entered "a golden age" during her term.¹⁰³ Chinese money funded several infrastructure and development projects in the Philippines accruing to US\$1.316 billion from 2001-2010 (term of office of Arroyo).¹⁰⁴

Finally, and probably the most significant of all, 9/11 happened and in its aftermath, the US rallied support for the global "War on Terror." The Arroyo government was quick to support the US and offered access to Clark Air Base and Subic Naval Base for US military operations. In return, the Philippines received increased military financing and support.¹⁰⁵

⁹⁸ Ibid.

⁹⁹ San Pablo-Baviera, A. (2002) 'The China Challenge to ASEAN Solidarity: The Case of the South China Sea Disputes'

¹⁰⁰ Ibid.

¹⁰¹ Buszynski, L. (2003) 'ASEAN, the Declaration on Conduct, and the South China Sea'

¹⁰² ASEAN (2012) 'Declaration on the Conduct of Parties in the South China Sea' [Online] http://asean.org/?static_post=declaration-on-the-conduct-of-parties-in-the-south-china-sea-2# (Accessed: 16 August 2017).

¹⁰³ Storey, I.J. (1999) 'Creeping Assertiveness: China, the Philippines and the South China Sea Dispute'

¹⁰⁴ De Guzman, C.J. (2014) 'Philippines-China Relations, 2001-2008: Dovetailing National Interests' *Asian Studies* (50:1), pp. 71-97.

¹⁰⁵ De Castro, R.C. (2007) 'China, the Philippines, and U.S. Influence in Asia' [Online] <http://www.aei.org/publication/china-the-philippines-and-u-s-influence-in-asia/> (Accessed: 4 July 2017).

This would have been a cause of concern for China, but...

[i]nstead of being intimidated by the revived U.S.-Philippine security relationship, China decided to join the counterterrorism bandwagon. A year after 9/11, Beijing offered to cooperate with Manila in “all fields of defense and armed forces which facilitate stability and the development of the region and the world at large.”¹⁰⁶

It may be surmised that China was not the power threatening the Philippines at that time. Instead, China was threatened by US unilateralism. While the target of the War on Terror was Al-Qaeda and its affiliates, the US’ increased military presence in South and Southeast Asia threatened to “strategically box in” China.¹⁰⁷

To prevent this, China engaged countries in the region, including the Philippines in positive and cooperative efforts. In addition to security cooperation, China provided significant loans to the Philippines with “easy payment terms” and favorable rates that could finance its economic development projects.¹⁰⁸ China even invited the Philippines to join the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, an anti-terrorism coalition.¹⁰⁹

Considering these developments (i.e., signing of the DOC, US unilateralism, a Filipino and Chinese government willing to engage), the Philippines and China saw an opportunity for cooperation in the South China Sea. In November 2003, the Philippine National Oil Company (PNOC) and the China National Offshore Oil Corporation (CNOOC) signed an agreement for joint exploration and development in the South China Sea; which culminated into the signing of the Joint Marine Seismic Undertaking (JMSU) in September 2004. This initially elicited protests from Vietnam, and so in March 2005, a tripartite agreement was signed among PNOC, CNOOC, and Petro Vietnam.¹¹⁰

The JMSU ran from 2005 to 2008, with the three countries jointly gathering and sharing seismic data to determine the amount of petroleum in a 142,886 kilometer-area in the west of Palawan.¹¹¹ The signing of JMSU also coincided with the falling out of relationship between the Philippines and the US, when the Philippines withdrew its troops from Iraq in July 2004 in exchange for the release of a kidnapped Filipino truck driver.¹¹²

The Arroyo government argued: (1) that the JMSU was necessary because of rising oil prices; (2) that it doesn’t alter the Philippines’ territorial claims; (3) that it is constitutional; and (4) that it is consistent with the DOC.¹¹³ The Chinese government also welcomed the JMSU. Strategically, it had opened new opportunities for China and it had effectively divided ASEAN on the issue of the South China Sea.¹¹⁴

However, the JMSU was not well received by the Filipino public. For one thing, it was signed in secret, and as such, was not subject to public scrutiny. It is criticized to have violated the Philippine Constitution considering that 80% of the exploration area lies within the country’s

¹⁰⁶ De Castro, R.C. (2007) ‘China, the Philippines, and U.S. Influence in Asia’

¹⁰⁷ Ibid.

¹⁰⁸ De Guzman, C.J. (2014) ‘Philippines-China Relations, 2001-2008: Dovetailing National Interests’

¹⁰⁹ De Castro, R.C. (2007) ‘China, the Philippines, and U.S. Influence in Asia’

¹¹⁰ De Guzman, C.J. (2014) ‘Philippines-China Relations, 2001-2008: Dovetailing National Interests’

¹¹¹ ABS-CBN News (2008) ‘Palace officials defend Spratly’s deal’ [Online] <http://news.abs-cbn.com/nation/03/07/08/palace-officials-defend-spratlys-deal> (Accessed: 14 August 2017).

¹¹² De Castro, R.C. (2007) ‘China, the Philippines, and U.S. Influence in Asia’

¹¹³ Storey, I.J. (1999) ‘Creeping Assertiveness: China, the Philippines and the South China Sea Dispute’

¹¹⁴ Bower, E.Z. (2010) ‘The JMSU: A Tale of Bilateralism and Secrecy in the South China Sea’ [Online] <https://www.csis.org/analysis/jmsu-tale-bilateralism-and-secrecy-south-china-sea> (Accessed: 14 August 2017).

200-nautical mile EEZ.¹¹⁵ Some opposition politicians even revealed that the JMSU was signed by the Philippine government in exchange for a US\$400 million Chinese loan for the North Luzon Railways Project.¹¹⁶ This revelation came at a time when the Arroyo government faced corruption allegations and controversies linked to loans from China.

The Philippines was also criticized for engaging China bilaterally, and in the process breaking ranks with ASEAN in tackling the South China Sea issue multilaterally. In 2008, after strong opposition from the Filipino public, the Arroyo government did not extend the JMSU.¹¹⁷

2012 Scarborough Shoal Standoff – Back to using Alliances and International Institutions

Philippines-China relations hit a setback with the non-extension of the JMSU and the passage of the baselines law by the Philippines in 2009 (to meet an UNCLOS deadline), which identified the country's archipelagic baselines and included Scarborough Shoal and the *Kalayaan Island Group* as part of a "regime of islands under the Republic of the Philippines."¹¹⁸ In the same year, China submitted its Nine-Dash Line claim to the UN.

And yet, up until the end of the Arroyo government and at the beginning of the Aquino government, the Philippines engaged China and tried to keep a friendly relationship. In fact, "[i]n late 2010, the Philippines joined a 19-state coalition led by China that boycotted the awarding ceremony in Oslo, Norway for Nobel Peace Prize winner, Chinese dissident Liu Xiaobo."¹¹⁹

However, Chinese actions in early 2011 which involved the harassment of Philippine survey ships conducting oil exploration in Reed Bank, drove the Aquino government into a balancing stance against China. A multi-year defense capability upgrade was approved by then-President Aquino, and in 2012, Congress extended the AFP modernization law passed in the 1990's.¹²⁰

The complete shift in Philippine policy towards China came in 2012. From April to June 2012, the Philippines and China were locked in a standoff in the Scarborough Shoal¹²¹; 136 miles from the Philippine province of Zambales and 497 miles from Hong Kong.¹²²

The incident began when a Philippine Navy surveillance plane saw several Chinese fishing vessels in the shoal, prompting the deployment of the warship BRP *Gregorio del Pilar* to make arrests. According to reports, Chinese fishermen in the shoal were illegally collecting corals, giant clams, and live sharks. However, before an arrest can be made, two Chinese maritime surveillance vessels arrived, positioned itself between the fishing vessels and the Philippine warship, and prevented the arrest of the fishermen.¹²³

To avoid an escalation of tension, the Philippines replaced the warship with a coast guard vessel, but China responded by deploying the *Yuzheng 310*, "its most advanced and largest patrol vessel equipped with machine guns, light cannons, and electronic sensors." China also asserted its claims diplomatically, when the Philippines protested the deployment, noting that

¹¹⁵ De Guzman, C.J. (2014) 'Philippines-China Relations, 2001-2008: Dovetailing National Interests'

¹¹⁶ ABS-CBN News (2008) 'Palace officials defend Spratly's deal'

¹¹⁷ De Guzman, C.J. (2014) 'Philippines-China Relations, 2001-2008: Dovetailing National Interests'

¹¹⁸ Buszynski, L. (2003) 'ASEAN, the Declaration on Conduct, and the South China Sea'

¹¹⁹ De Castro, R.C. (2016) 'Twenty-First Century Philippines' Policy Toward an Emergent China: From Equi-Balancing to Strategic Balancing' *Asian Politics & Policy* (8:2), pp. 305-328

¹²⁰ Ibid.

¹²¹ Ibid.

¹²² Inquirer (2012) 'Scarborough shoal standoff: A timeline'

¹²³ Miks, J. (2012) 'China, Philippines in Standoff' [Online] <http://thediplomat.com/2012/04/china-philippines-in-standoff/> (Accessed: 30 June 2017).

Scarborough Shoal “is an integral part of the Chinese territory and the waters around it are the traditional fishing areas for Chinese fishermen.”¹²⁴

China also quarantined bananas imported from the Philippines and issued a travel ban that saw the cancellation of several trips to the Philippines by Chinese tour groups. These actions were designed to put pressure on the Philippine government to withdraw from the Scarborough Shoal, considering that around 200,000 were employed in the banana industry with around 70% of their exports going to China.¹²⁵ However, China’s actions and the pressure exerted on the Philippine government, instead of intimidating it, produced a “rally-around effect.”

At the height of the stand-off, the Philippines’ fractious power blocs, as well as the normally apathetic public, became united and solidly swung behind the government as Philippine civilian vessels confronted their Chinese counterparts at the Scarborough Shoal.¹²⁶

In addition, the Philippines appealed to the US for support and during the standoff, a Virginia-class fast attack submarine arrived at Subic Bay, sending a message to China that the US will support the Philippines militarily in case of armed conflict. The Philippines also called on ASEAN to take a common position against China’s assertiveness in the South China Sea.¹²⁷

The two-month long standoff ended in June after an agreement was reached that saw Philippine and Chinese vessels leaving the shoal in a “carefully choreographed withdrawal,” citing the rough seas due to seasonal typhoons as justification.¹²⁸

However, instead of the relations between the Philippines and China normalizing, it further deteriorated when after the recent tension eased, China “constructed a chain barrier across the mouth of the shoal to block any Philippine access to it. China also deployed [maritime surveillance vessels] to protect the fleet of Chinese fishing boats operating deep into the Philippines’ EEZ.”¹²⁹

In response, the Philippines continued to engage ASEAN for a common position on the disputes as well as a common position against China’s unilateral actions; reasserting that all parties who are signatories to the 2002 DOC uphold their commitments; and for ASEAN, as the preponderant regional grouping, to encourage all parties to resolve disputes by peaceful means, without resorting to the use of force, and in accordance with international law. Furthermore, the Philippines engaged ASEAN to encourage China to conclude a more legally binding COC.

To recall, the Philippines extended the armed forces modernization law in 2012, and the Philippine military received increased allocation to develop their capability in order to respond to external threats.¹³⁰ Among the acquired military assets of the Philippines are two Weather High Endurance Cutters, several helicopters, and 12 FA-50 aircraft.¹³¹

¹²⁴ De Castro, R.C. (2016) ‘Twenty-First Century Philippines’ Policy Toward an Emergent China: From Equi-Balancing to Strategic Balancing’

¹²⁵ Ibid.

¹²⁶ Ibid.

¹²⁷ Ibid.

¹²⁸ Perlez, J. (2012) ‘Philippines and China Ease Tensions in Rift at Sea’ [Online]

<http://www.nytimes.com/2012/06/19/world/asia/beijing-and-manila-ease-tensions-in-south-china-sea.html> (Accessed: 15 August 2017).

¹²⁹ De Castro, R.C. (2016) ‘Twenty-First Century Philippines’ Policy Toward an Emergent China: From Equi-Balancing to Strategic Balancing’

¹³⁰ De Castro, R.C. (2016) ‘Twenty-First Century Philippines’ Policy Toward an Emergent China: From Equi-Balancing to Strategic Balancing’

¹³¹ Office of the President of the Philippines (2015) ‘The 2015 State of the Nation Address Technical Report’ [Online] <http://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2015/07/27/2015-sona-technical-report/> (Accessed: 12 August 2017).

Two more significant balancing acts were undertaken by the Philippines: (1) it initiated arbitration against China in early 2013¹³²; and (2) it began negotiations with the US in August 2013 for a framework agreement that would facilitate the deployment of US troops and equipment in the Philippines on a rotational basis, later called the Enhanced Defense Cooperation Agreement (EDCA).¹³³

As a response to these two significant developments, China accelerated its timeline in controlling the area by undertaking massive land reclamation in late 2013, which turned submerged reefs into islands.¹³⁴ The US estimates that around 3,200 acres has been reclaimed in the Spratly Islands, with China installing military hardware on these artificial islands, including airstrips, port facilities, and missiles.¹³⁵

The Philippines continued with its diplomatic offensives, and brought the issue in the international fora, which garnered the support of the US, Japan, the EU, Australia, and New Zealand. Also, in June 2015, the G7 leaders in its Summit Declaration noted the tensions in the South China Sea and opposed China's use of force, including unilateral actions such as land reclamations, in the pursuit of its claims.¹³⁶ These efforts aimed to highlight that China is not behaving like a responsible member of the international community, and that its military and economic might does not necessarily make its actions right and legal.

More importantly, the Philippines and the US concluded the negotiations on EDCA in April 2014. EDCA is a deterrence posture against China, wherein US forces and military hardware are allowed access to the Philippines and may immediately be mobilized in case of rising tension or conflict in the South China Sea.¹³⁷ The US also continually conducts Freedom of Navigation Operations (FONOPS) to challenge China's claims and assertions in the South China Sea, especially in reclaimed islands.¹³⁸

The Philippines and Japan also declared in 2015 that their relations entered into a "Strengthened Strategic Partnership," which involves the transfer of defense equipment and technology from Japan to the Philippines; mutually beneficial economic partnership; and diplomatic support for the Philippines' position against unilateral actions, peaceful settlement of disputes, and adherence to international law in the South China Sea.¹³⁹

Vietnam also entered into a "Strategic Partnership" with the Philippines in November 2015, with then-President Truong noting both their countries' concerns over the recent developments in the South China Sea.¹⁴⁰

¹³² Permanent Court of Arbitration (2016) 'Press Release: The South China Sea Arbitration' [Online] <https://pca-cpa.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/175/2016/07/PH-CN-20160712-Press-Release-No-11-English.pdf> (Accessed: 30 June 2017).

¹³³ De Castro, R.C. (2016) 'Twenty-First Century Philippines' Policy Toward an Emergent China: From Equi-Balancing to Strategic Balancing'

¹³⁴ BBC News (2015) 'China 'must stop' land reclamation in South China Sea – Obama' [Online] <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-asia-34853878> (Accessed: 15 August 2017).

¹³⁵ Allen-Ebrahimian, B. (2016) 'Beijing Calls South China Sea Island Reclamation a 'Green Project'' [Online] <http://foreignpolicy.com/2016/05/26/china-calls-south-china-sea-island-reclamation-a-green-project-spratly-islands/> (Accessed: 15 August 2017).

¹³⁶ Office of the President of the Philippines (2015) 'The 2015 State of the Nation Address Technical Report'

¹³⁷ De Castro, R.C. (2016) 'Twenty-First Century Philippines' Policy Toward an Emergent China: From Equi-Balancing to Strategic Balancing'

¹³⁸ Ali, I. and Brunnstrom, D. (2017) 'U.S. warship drill meant to defy China's claim over artificial island: officials' [Online] <http://www.reuters.com/article/us-usa-southchinasea-navy-idUSKBN18K353> (Accessed: 23 August 2017).

¹³⁹ Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan (2015) 'Japan-Philippines Joint Declaration: A Strengthened Strategic Partnership for Advancing the Shared Principles and Goals of Peace, Security, and Growth in the Region and Beyond' [Online] http://www.mofa.go.jp/sa/sea2/ph/page4e_000280.html (Accessed: 8 July 2017).

¹⁴⁰ Sabillo, K.A. (2015) 'PH, Vietnam ink closer defense ties' [Online] <http://globalnation.inquirer.net/131451/ph-vietnam-sign-statement-on-strategic-partnership-amid-disputes-in-south-china-sea> (Accessed: 8 July 2017).

A big diplomatic victory for the Philippines came in 2016 when it won the arbitration against China. The Tribunal found that China's Nine-Dash Line was incompatible with the provisions of UNCLOS, and that its claim to "historic rights" were extinguished with UNCLOS.¹⁴¹

However, the award came just after a leadership change in the Philippines, with the Duterte administration bandwagoning with China.

Summary

CASES	PREMISE	CHINA'S ACTIONS	PH RESPONSE	OUTCOME
1994/ 1995 Mischief Reef occupation and its aftermath	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fall of the Soviet Union • Cancellation of US bases in the Philippines in 1991 • China's 1992 Law on Territorial Sea and Contiguous Zones • 1992 Manila Declaration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Occupation of Mischief Reef • Continued poaching and encroachment on Philippine waters • Building more permanent structures in Mischief Reef in 1998 	<p><u>Hard Balancing</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passage of AFP modernization law • VFA with the US <p><u>Soft Balancing</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internationalized the issue • Engaged ASEAN to condemn Chinese action • Engaged ASEAN in negotiating with China for a COC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1995 Philippines-China agreement on a code of conduct • Continued Chinese occupation of Mischief Reef and encroachment in Philippine waters • Signing of the DOC in 2002 • The US' return in Philippine waters
Cooperation through JMSU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 9/11 • 2002 DOC • A Philippine president seeking to engage China 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • China-PH Security cooperation • Provided favorable loans to PH • Signed the JMSU 	<p><u>Engagement</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic engagement of China • Signed the JMSU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JMSU (2005-2008), but was not extended
2012 Scarborough Shoal standoff and its aftermath	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-extension of JMSU • Philippines' 2009 baselines law • China's Nine-Dash Line declaration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continued encroachment on Philippine waters; and harassment of Philippine fishermen and oil exploration vessels • Scarborough Shoal standoff • Massive land reclamation in its controlled features in the Spratly Islands 	<p><u>Hard Balancing</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extended the AFP modernization law and acquired naval and air force assets • EDCA with the US • Strengthened strategic partnership with Japan and Vietnam <p><u>Soft Balancing</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internationalized the issue • Engaged ASEAN to abide by the DOC, to condemn China's actions, and to engage it for a COC • Filed and won the arbitration case 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arbitration delegitimized China's Nine-Dash Line claim and called attention to its violations of international law and the sovereign rights of the Philippines • China negotiates with ASEAN for a COC • China has militarized its occupied features and established better control of the area • Greater involvement of the US in the South China Sea

¹⁴¹ Permanent Court of Arbitration (2016) 'Press Release: The South China Sea Arbitration'

Synthesis

Among China's motivations in its actions in the South China Sea is the fear of the Communist party to be displaced from power through external actions by the US operating in the area. China is surrounded by US allies (Japan, South Korea, the Philippines, among others), and among its fears is a strategic blockade of the South China Sea that would choke trade, the source of its wealth, and thus power. It may be recalled that the Communist party regained their credibility with the people, after Tiananmen Square, when they were able to lift them out of poverty. As such, trade is important to keep the Chinese content, and prevent an upheaval due to poverty and high cost of goods.

In the quest of protecting itself, China has threatened small states like the Philippines. But China has its own fears, and this may be taken as insight in how the Philippines manages the issue.

The Philippines has the option to balance against China and several tools are at its disposal in balancing, foremost of which is its alliance with the US that may deter further aggression. Deterrence is one thing, but it may be difficult to leverage the alliance in diplomatic negotiations, since the US will not step in to assert Philippine claims.

Thus, the Philippines should not just rely on the US. It should also pursue improving its own capability, building up its air force and naval assets, as well as, modernizing the coast guard. This is so that at the point of conflict, it has the assets to holdoff the threatening power.

In the 2012 Scarborough Shoal standoff, though the warship was immediately replaced by a civilian coast guard vessel to lessen the tension, those assets were instrumental in getting China into a standoff and asserting the Philippines' territorial integrity on the ground (or on water). The said standoff forced China into diplomatic negotiations with the Philippines to resolve the situation.

Moreover, increasing the Philippines' capability will improve its ability to enforce its laws within its jurisdiction and make it costly for Chinese vessels to encroach on Philippine waters.

Aside from military build-up and alliance formation, international institutions that promote the rule of law, regional peace and stability, peaceful settlement of disputes, and respect for sovereign rights are tools available to the Philippines. In fact, it has availed itself of these in its engagement with ASEAN and in filing arbitration against China.

In the end, the Philippines' smallness in the face of a big China, should not be a hindrance in asserting its sovereign rights and in calling China to account; calling on the international community to pressure China into following international law and behave like a responsible member of the international community of nations.